

Original Article: Comparison of Organizational Citizenship Behavior and Job Creativity between Male and Men's Education Personnel 1 Ahvaz

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was to compare organizational citizenship behavior and job creativity between male and female education personnel in Ahvaz District; the statistical population of this study included all the statistical population of all male and female education of Ahvaz District, with about 5 people. The sample of this study consists of 5 male and female educators in Ahvaz District 2, which was used to choose from class sampling and in terms of Morgan's table. The selected method of this type of research is a comparison of the post-event type. The tools used in this study were the Questionnaire of Citizen Citizenship Behavior and Randip Creativity Questionnaire. The findings showed that, given the averages of the two groups, female prost had higher organizational citizenship behavior than male nurses. Given the average temperature of the two groups, male pistols have more job creativity than female personnel.

Introduction

One of the most important features of any organization to work in variable conditions is to have people who are able to participate in the successful

changes of the organization without formal job requirements. Behaviors that have come from formal expectations but are very important and necessary for the survival of the organization and are defined as citizenship behaviors.

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Organizations are unable to develop their effectiveness without the desire of people to cooperate. The difference between self-boiling and mandatory cooperation is of particular importance. In mandatory state, the individual performs his or her duties in accordance with the rules and regulations and standards of the organization and solely in accordance with the requirements. While in their own and conscious cooperation of individuals, they use their efforts, energy and insight to flourish their capabilities in favor of the organization, in the current competitive conditions, the extent of participation, obedience and loyalty to the organization. It is very important. Accordingly, the results of the studies show that employees require voluntary morale, friendship, respect, and respect for the proper functioning and strengthening it. One of these new concepts is expanding and entirely related to such transnational behaviors of organizational citizenship behavior that has attracted the attention of researchers and managers of organizations as an effective factor in the organization (1)

In the organization of organization and management, individual and voluntary behaviors that are not designed directly by formal pads are called organizational citizenship behavior, which is effective in promoting effectiveness and efficiency. By definition, human beings as an organizational mayor are expected to serve the goals of the organization more than the requirements of their role and beyond the formal duties. Successful organizations need employees who work more than their usual duties and have a performance beyond the expectations of the organization. Organizational citizenship behavior describes measures in which employees go beyond their predetermined needs, which increase organizational effectiveness (Abbil, 1) Every organization needs various resources to achieve its goals, and undoubtedly the most important resource in any human resources organization working in that organization. Many factors affect individuals' efficiency in the organization One of the things that greatly affects the organizational behavior of each individual is creativity. Creativity is necessary for the survival of each

organization, and the creativity literature in the field of organization briefly represents categories. There are various factors affecting creativity that affect people's creativity and innovation from within and outside the organization. Nowadays, all organizations need new ideas and new ideas. New thoughts and opinions are seen as a spirit in the organization and save it from nothingness and mortality. Stanberg considers creativity to be new communication, seeing things through new and new definitions. The atmosphere of the organization has a significant relationship with creativity, and the culture and essence of the organization and the institution may participate as a factor in the amount of creativity and innovation in that institution or organization. Research has shown that the atmosphere of the organization can affect people's creativity and innovation, the more open the organization's atmosphere, the more creativity and the climate of the organization becomes less creative and innovation (2-4)

Jafari, Sadeghi and Khodari Zarnegh (1) investigated the relationship between organizational citizenship behavior and organizational commitment of male and female staff at Shahid Hashemi Nejad Hospital in Tehran and showed that most of the individuals under investigation (5-7) evaluated the status of citizenship behavior as appropriate. There was a significant statistical relationship between organizational citizenship and organizational commitment. Among the dimensions of organizational citizenship behavior, there was a significant relationship between the dimensions of radical and civic virtue and the organizational commitment, but there was no significant relationship between the dimensions of literature and tract, the conscience and the type of friendship with the organizational commitment. There is a significant difference

Ghorbenian, Makarem, Hosseini and Bakhshi (8) examined the correlation between responsibility and organizational citizenship behavior in male and female staff of the Tehran Welfare Organization and showed that there was a positive and significant correlation between the responsibility and organizational behavior of employees. Also, among the

dimensions of organizational citizenship behavior, the type of friendship, civil virtue, and conscientiousness with responsibility was meaningful and positive. There was a difference between the responsibility of male and female employees, but there was no difference between the organizational behavior of male and female employees: Barzin: Muammar & Alipour, (9) to examine the relationship between emotional intelligence and job satisfaction and creativity and innovation The Department of Education of West Azerbaijan has shown that emotional intelligence is positively and significantly related to job satisfaction, creativity and innovation. There is a positive and significant relationship between job satisfaction and creativity and innovation. There is a difference between job satisfaction and creativity and innovation of men and women. Emotional intelligence predicts job satisfaction, creativity and innovation, as well as the amount of creativity and innovation of flax work by increasing their job satisfaction. Dehghani and Mazaheri (10) examined the relationship between creativity and job satisfaction and mental health at the time of the nurse and showed that there was a significant negative correlation between anxiety symptoms and the development of creativity. There was also a significant negative correlation between the symptoms of depression and the satisfaction of the nature of the work, and between the symptoms of social functioning with respect to the nature of the work, the satisfaction of the nature of the work, and the total score of the job dancer. The difference between the average scores of married nurses and single nurses in physical symptoms and anxiety symptoms of mental health and the initiative and flexibility of creativity were significant. Shojaee and Norouzi (11) examined the relationship between organizational justice and organizational commitment with organizational citizenship behavior and concluded that organizational justice could play a very moral role in developing and improving organizational citizenship behavior in organizational behavior to those behavior to those citizenship behavior to those behavior. Behaviors note that there is no compulsion from the organization to do so and that the activities of the employees will benefit

the organization. It is an organizational commitment that requires a person to fulfill his or her duties in the organization to fulfill his or her organizational goals. Agai et al. The findings of the study indicate that job exhaustion affects organizational and organizational citizenship behavior, organizational atmosphere on job burnout and organizational citizenship behavior, organizational culture on job burnout, organizational citizenship behavior, and organizational climate. On the other hand, organizational citizenship behavior is the most influential and organizational culture is the most influential variables.

In their research, Mantou and Manicandan (12) concluded that organizational citizenship behaviors and organizational justice have a direct and direct impact on anti-productive work behavior. This is the reason that when organizational citizenship behaviors and organizational justice in the organization are at a high level, anti-productive work behavior will be at the lowest level. Taii (13) tested the impact of profit partnership programs on organizational citizenship behaviors and the modulating role of organizational commitment in three IT-related companies in Taiwan, and badly concluded that the organizational commitment between participation programs in profit and behavior. Adjusts organizational citizenship. In other words, the greater the organizational commitment in individuals, the greater the profit of the Citizenship Partnership Programs become more citizenship in the work of Philip *et al.* (14). Encourage organizational and raising the perception of the book's work of justice. Only employees reach a high level of organizational citizenship when their perception of organizational justice and organizational effectiveness is at high levels (15) Occupational satisfaction, understanding of justice and organizational commitment to organizational citizenship behaviors examined. He gave. The results of his research showed that only organizational commitment was related to organizational citizenship behaviors. In their research, Manju and Manicandan (16) concluded that organizational citizenship behaviors and organizational justice have a direct and direct impact on production behavior.

This is the reason that when organizational citizenship behaviors and organizational justice in the organization are at high levels, anti-productive behavior behavior will be at the lowest level Diciton *et al.* (17) in a study concluded that attitudinal variables including job satisfaction, relationship with the prevailing , Perception of appointment, organizational commitment, and so on. The results showed that the semen between the relationship with the superiors, organizational commitment and work stress with organizational citizenship behavior. Also, the results of the hypotheses test did not show the modest relationship between job satisfaction, perception of appointment and stress at home with organizational citizenship behavior. Therefore, according to the material presented, the purpose of this study is to compare responsibility, organizational citizenship behavior and job creativity between male and female education in Ahwaz District.

materials and ways Ali Research Method is a post-event comparison of the statistical population in this study. The sample of this study consists of 5 male and female educators in Ahwaz District 2, which was used to choose from class sampling and in terms of Morgan's table. The data collection tool is a questionnaire in this research:

Organizational Citizenship Behavior Questionnaire: This questionnaire, which is used to measure staff citizenship behavior, Pedsakov *et al.* (18), with the help of a factor analysis method for each of the five dimensions of organizational citizenship behavior, created a standard measurement scale (questionnaire These scales have been used by many researchers and researchers to measure organizational citizenship behavior (19) This questionnaire consists of 4 options: Conscience,

courtesy, kindness, kindness Citizenship and Citizenship Fats are the areas of this questionnaire, which are the number of options in each area: Working conscience (2 options), courtesy and kindness, and the type of friendship (2 options), charm (2 options) and virtue of citizenship. (2 options). (20) In the present study to determine the reliability of the Organizational Citizenship Behavioral Questionnaire, use the Cronbach Ronah, which for the entire questionnaire of $1\sqrt{2}$, indicating the favorable reliability coefficients of the questionnaire.

The job creativity questionnaire was used by the Randsip Creativity Questionnaire to measure researchers' creativity score. The questionnaire was invented by Randsip and was published in the Journal of Employees in Year 2. This questionnaire consists of 2 questions and each question is rated as a five-value Likert scale (1 = I fully agree: 1 = I agree: 1 Bi-Manicar: 1: I disagree: 1: I am totally disagree. The Randsip scoring method has been determined between 1 and 2, which represents higher creativity, and the score is such that Moghimi, 1): Score 1 to 2 = Very Creative, Nusra 1 to 2 = High School Creativity 2 Up to 1 = Moderate Creativity, Nushes 1 to 2 Creativity less than secondary grade ranging from 1 to 2 = non-creative in the present study was used to determine the reliability of the Cronbah Alfa Creativity Questionnaire. The desired is the questionnaire.

Findings

Descriptive findings of this study include statistical indicators such as mean, standard deviation for all variables studied in this study in Table 1.

Table 1. Descriptive findings of this study include statistical indicators such as mean, standard deviation for all variables studied

Number	Conventional deviation	average	Statistical indicators	variable
120	13/32	70/06	Female staff	Organizational citizenship behavior
180	11/64	67/68	Male personnel	
300	12/47	70/87	All staff	
120	4/11	18/60	Female staff	Conscience
180	3/31	16/08	Male personnel	

300	3/96	17/84	All staff	Politeness
120	3/05	16/24	Female staff	
180	3/42	15/11	Male personnel	
300	5/81	15/43	All staff	Component
120	4/52	19/22	Female staff	
180	4/87	17/82	Male personnel	
300	3/58	18/52	All staff	The component of charm
120	2/46	13/00	Female staff	
180	2/50	11/16	Male personnel	
300	5/05	12/08	All staff	Citizenship
120	4/86	15/84	Female staff	
180	4/46	14/68	Male personnel	
300	11/72	14/67	All staff	Job creativity
120	13/55	59/94	Female staff	
180	12/64	64/56	Male personnel	
300		63/25	All staff	

As can be seen in Table (1) in Organizational Citizenship Variable, female personnel, $74\sqrt{74}$, $21\sqrt{11}$ male personnel $68\sqrt{68}$ and 11.64 and total staff of $70\sqrt{70\sqrt{47}}$, in citizenship variable Organization for Working Conscience, Female Personnel, $16\sqrt{18}$ and $11\sqrt{11}$, Male Personnel $08\sqrt{16}$ and $331\sqrt{3}$ and Total Personnel $84\sqrt{17}$ and $85\sqrt{8}$, in Organizational Citizenship variable, female personnel $24\sqrt{16}$ and $96\sqrt{3}$, male personnel $11\sqrt{11}$ and 3.05 and the total staff of 12.43 and total staff of 18.52 and $4\sqrt{87}$, in organizational citizenship variable in the field of charm, female personnel 008 and 58.58, Male personnel $16\sqrt{11}$ and 2.6 and total staff of

$12\sqrt{12}$ and 2.50, in organizational citizenship variable in the field of citizenship virtue, female personnel $15\sqrt{15}$ and 5.05, male personnel $14\sqrt{14}$ and $4\sqrt{86}$ and 4.86 The total staff is $12\sqrt{14}$ and 46.46 and in the variable of job creativity, female personnel is 59.94 and 112.72, 66.56 and $125\sqrt{55}$ and the total staff is 63.25 and 12.64.

The present study contains the following hypotheses, each with the results obtained from its analysis. The first hypothesis: There is a difference between organizational citizenship behavior between male and female nurses.

Table 2. The present study contains the following hypotheses, each with the results obtained from its analysis

Level Meaning) p)	f	DF	DF	the amount of Results	Name Test
0/0001	26/28	296	3	0/832	Impact test
0/0001	26/28	296	3	0/412	Wilks Lambada Test
0/0001	26/28	296	3	0/871	Hoteling Test
0/0001	26/28	296	3	0/871	The biggest root test

Hypothesis 2: There is a difference between the amount of job creativity between the male and female. As shown in Table (2), the significant levels of all tests indicate that there is a significant difference between male and female nurses in terms of one of the variables of

authority, organizational citizenship behavior, and job creativity $f = 26\sqrt{28}$, $p = 0\sqrt{0001}$ To find out the request, the results of a variable variance analysis in Manava are presented in Table (3).

Table 3: Variable Variable Variety Analysis Results in Manava's Text on Organizational Citizenship Variables and Job Creativity Between male and female personnel

Level You mean	f	Average Regarding	Degrees of freedom	Total Regarding	Variables
0/0001	12/580	2962/26	1	2962/26	Organizational citizenship behavior
0/0001	10/729	2225/78	1	2225/78	Job creativity

As in Table (3), it is observed that there is a significant difference between male and female nurses in terms of organizational citizenship behavior at $1/2$ p and), so the second hypothesis is confirmed. In other words, given the averages of the two groups, female personnel have a higher organizational citizenship than male nurses than male and female, there is a significant difference in job creativity. Therefore, the second hypothesis is confirmed. In other words, due to the averages of the two groups, male pistols have more job creativity than female nurses.

Discussion

The purpose of the present study was to compare the responsibility of organizational citizenship behavior and job creativity between male and female personnel in Ahwaz District, according to which two Fried were compiled, which were discussed and explained. As in Table (1): There is a significant difference between male and female personnel in terms of organizational citizenship behavior. In other words, given the averages of the two groups, female personnel have higher organizational citizenship behavior than male nurses, as well as between male and female nurses in terms of organizational citizenship components in terms of conscience. In other words, given the averages of the two groups, female nurses are more likely to have organizational citizenship behavior in the field of conscience than male. There is a significant difference between male and female nurses in terms of organizational citizenship behavior in terms of politeness. In other words, given the averages of the two groups, female permeables are more polite than the male citizenship. There is a significant difference between male and female nurses in terms of organizational citizenship components in the type of friendship. In other words, given the

averages of the two groups, its personnel are more likely to be friendly than male personnel. There is a significant difference between male and female personnel in terms of organizational citizenship components in the field of charm. In other words, given the average of the two women's nursing groups, they have a higher organizational behavior in the field of chivalry than the male nurses. There is a significant difference between male and female nurses in terms of partying of organizational citizenship in the field of citizenship virtue. In other words, according to the average of the two groups, female personnel have more organizational citizenship behavior than male personnel.

This finding is the findings of Jafari, Sadeghi and Khodayari Zaranagh (2015), Jorbanian, Makarem, Hosseini and Bakhshi (2014) Shojaei and Norouzi (2013), Aghaei *et al.* (2013), Taghipour and Khodadadnejad (2012), Kazemi (2011), Sohrabizadeh, Bastani and Ravangard (2010), Manjo and Manikandan (2013), Tasai (2012), Philip *et al.* (2012) are similar.

Explaining this hypothesis, it can be said that one of the most important characteristics of any organization to work in conditions of change is to have people who are willing to participate in the successful changes of the organization, the existence of formal job requirements. Behaviors that exceed the formal expectations of the role but are very financial and even necessary for the survival of the organization and are expressed as citizenship behaviors. Organizations are able to develop their effectiveness without cooperation. Self-compulsory from an important and important cooperation in a different compulsory state, performs its duties in accordance with the rules, regulations and standards set by the organization and only to the extent of complying with the requirements. While in cooperation with spontaneous and conscious people, they use their efforts, energy and insight to flourish to

silver companies (21). Strengthen citizenship behaviors for communication, reduce workload, stay loyal to the organization, pay, pay attention to the organization's services, and so on. According to Williams (1999), behaviors that go beyond the requirements described for the role and are beneficial to the organization are seen as an unacceptable need for organizational performance. Organizational citizenship behavior is seen as a desirable situation because such behavior on the one hand increases the available resources and direction, and on the other hand gives impetus to formal and costly control mechanisms, and Haqqari Ashtiani is citizenship behavior, productivity. And increases workgroups, increases teamwork, increases communication and assistance between people, reduces and increases error rates, and organizes and engages people in issues. Give. In general, the improvement of morale, organizational growth, job satisfaction, job loss reduction, absenteeism, destructive job behaviors, as well as the impact on improving external factors such as customer satisfaction, service quality and service loyalty leads to excellent quality. It becomes job performance. According to the results of this fat showed that female personnel died more than personnel from citizenship behavior.

As shown in Table (2). There is a significant difference between male and female Prestel in terms of job creativity. In other words, according to the averages of the two groups, male Prestels have more job creativity than female Prestels. This finding is in line with the findings of Amjadi Barzin Moammar and Alipour, (2014), Dehghani and Mazaheri (2013), Ansari (2010), Omidi *et al.* (2007); In explaining this hypothesis, it can be said that the survival of any organization depends on its dynamic interaction with the internal and external environment. As a result of this interaction, the latest information and findings of human sciences and technologies are found and lead to changes in organizational practices and behavior. Also, in this interaction, the organization must obtain sufficient and required resources and make the necessary synchronization with the real requests of the environment. Habban, the organization depends to a large extent on the skills and awareness of

employees. The more timely and optimal these areas are, the greater the ability to adapt to a negative environment. Training and development of human resources not only plays an important role in creating special knowledge and skills of employees, but also helps people to improve efficiency and effectiveness. Be a part of the Semitic organization and adapt to changing environmental pressures (22). Creativity deals with creating and finding new ideas and innovations in the application of ideas. From a managerial point of view, cost-effective creativity is not enough. Thought must also be put into action, and this requires the application of new ideas in management programs. Every successful planning requires practical thought and ideas. The ultimate success and in some cases the survival of the organization itself depends on the ability of the planner to create and apply new ideas. If a person does not know where he wants to go, he will reach whatever destination he chooses. Since the existence of organizations is to provide, so these goals must be set and the ways to provide them must be identified.

Conclusion

Creativity and innovation is something that is constantly needed in the organization. Therefore, it must be institutionalized and become part of the work and culture of the organization. As long as top managers and policy makers of the organization do not believe in creativity and innovation as essential and vital activities, no activity in this field will last. Creating research and innovation centers in the organization can facilitate and accelerate the work of creativity and innovation. Creating shared beliefs for innovation and being seen as a common norm in the organization requires training. Toffler considers education to be the most important activity and way of coping with great changes and future life to accept change. Effective and rich training helps people to achieve sufficient growth and ability in their jobs and work more efficiently. Managers should know that one of the important goals in education in the turbulent and changing environment of Ketoui is to learn the methods of creativity and innovation. For this purpose, it is

possible to accustom employees to thinking through training, and as a result, this thinking penetrates as an organizational culture in different layers of the organization and has a general and permanent impact on the implementation of organizational strategies. The subject of creativity and innovation is essential for organizational life and the continuation of their survival in a competitive world and complex domestic and international markets. In this situation, if an organization does not take serious action for innovation and disobedience, it will definitely fail; Because the development of science and technology and the arrival of new goods and products is so great that non-dynamic organizations without creativity and innovation, very quickly leave the scene of competition and lose the opportunity to compete and be with RFBA and become an organization. Are closed and isolated, which causes the organization to lag behind the organization and get out of competition. To prevent organizations from becoming a closed and isolated organization, organizations should instill the spirit of creativity and innovation in their body, and in the meantime, employees and experts of the organization should always take steps towards creativity and innovation, and as mentioned in the article. This is what I believe in organizational culture. Also, spreading the culture that managers will not be able to stay in the organization without observing innovation is an inevitable necessity in our current society. Managers should also pay attention to reforming organizational processes and creating a proper performance appraisal system, to spread creativity and innovation in all levels of the organization and among all employees to ultimately have a creative and innovative organization. It also showed that by changing the way of looking at the employees and experts of the organization, paying attention to the results of this fat, it is shown that male Prestels have more professional creativity than female personnel.

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